

MEMORANDUM

To: The Chairman and Members of the Parliamentary select committee on constitutional, legal and Parliamentary Affairs, parliament House, Accra.

Thro: The Parliamentary service of Ghana Accra.

From: A Concerned Citizen.

Subject: Promotion of Proper Human Sexual Rights and Ghanaian Family Values Bill, 2021.

Date: October 21, 2021

Introduction:

By a public notice, dated September 15, 2021 the parliamentary Service of Ghana, on behalf of the Parliamentary Select Committee on Constitutional, Legal, and Parliamentary Affairs, requested for memoranda on: “The Promotion of Proper Human Sexual Rights and Ghanaian Family Values Bill, 2021”. It is in reponse to this request by the Parliamentary service, that I, [REDACTED], a concerned citizen of Ghana, and a THINKER, submit this memorandum, in support of the Bill.

Body Content:

Re: The 1992 Constitution of Ghana

The values enacted in the constitution are couched in letters, which allow for easy comprehension by all well-meaning persons. Some of the constitution’s ultimate values are also discernible from THE SPIRIT OF THE CONSTITUTION. However, the letters, and the spirit of the constitution ore not mutually exclusive. Since the promulgation of the 1992 constitution, and throughout the Fourth Republic of Ghana, the Letters of the Constitution as well as the spirit of the constitution have been evoked, on their individual merits, as well as in tandem with each other to put an agreeable finality is debates in Parliament.

Through the interpretation of the constitution, it has been stressed that the enjoyment of all rights must be balanced with all the obligations that go with them.

1. The constituents Assembly of 1992

The framers of the 1992 Constitution very advisedly, set the tone for the spirit of the constitution to be evoked when needs be, to determine the proper course of salient parliamentary debates.

Thus, the 1992 constituent Assembly, devoted considerable time, space, and substance, to eventually debar our chiefs from participating in Partisan Politics, notwithstanding the fact that the constitution acknowledges the inalienable rights of the chiefs to enjoy Freedom of Association. However, the same constitution has determined that the participation of our chiefs in Active Politics is inimical to the assurance of the peace and tranquillity of their own traditional areas, in particular, including Ghana as a whole.

This proscription of our chiefs from participating in active politics in spite of their right to freedom of association is geared towards enabling the generality of the people in the traditional areas to enjoy their Right to Self-Determination, Peace and Tranquillity. The constitution itself has thus, set the president for the suppression of the Right of Association, of groups, or concerns operating in Ghana.

2. The Proscription of the “Church of Jesus Christ of Dzorwulu”

One major percept of the erstwhile Church of Jesus Christ of Dzorwulu was that all their faithfuls should enter the church premises for worship solely in their nakedness (both male and female, as well as children). In this regard, it goes without saying that both the leadership and the members could enjoy all other rights along with their Religious Rights as proclaimed under the UN Universal Declaration of Human Rights.

However, the Ghanaian Parliamentarians of those days which incidentally, promulgated the 1992 constitution, along with the Ghana Government of the day proscribed the Church of Jesus Christ of Dzorwulu, and razed down their church building, including all properties therein. That church has since, not resurrected. The charges preferred against the church of Jesus Christ of Dzorwulu included: “Complicity in the Promotion of Improper Human Values, Consistent with, Normal Ghanaian way of Life.”

3. The BOKO HARAM in West Africa

I understand that the Hausa phrase “Boko Haram” means “Book or Education is Evil”, (Please correct me, if I am wrong). Out of the desire of the faithful’s of Boko Haram to frustrate the educational system in Nigeria, (where their operations started) they have armed themselves to the teeth, running havoc and committing arson on educational establishments. Their operations are characterised by mass abduction, of predominantly school girls in order to frustrate and strangle their education.

Indeed, if the members of the Boko Haram had simply decided not to avail themselves of modern education nobody would have bothered themselves too much, to restrain them, from so-doing. However, Boko Haram are armed to the teeth, to wreak havoc on Educational Systems, and civilians, including innocent women, girls, and children. In response, the Nigerian Parliament enacted a bill in Parliament to deal with the menace of Boko Haram. This bill has enabled the

government of the Federal Republic of Nigeria to declare a state of emergency, that has subsequently enabled the Nigerian Army and the Nigerian Police Force to assemble the necessary armaments to root-out the Boko Haram menace. The ongoing military action of the Nigerian Military and the Police Forces enjoy the full support of the international community.

4. LGBTQI++ in Ghana: A declaration of intent to wage global genocide

If an eligible bachelor decides to “marry” and have “sex” with another eligible bachelor, their union will eventually perish childless. Similarly the “marriage” between two eligible Spinsters will end up being childless. If, for instance, all the current and subsequent eligible bachelors and spinsters on this earth decide to follow the status-quo of the LGBTQ’s++ all of them will likewise die childless. After some decades the eventual annihilation of humanity, the genus “Homo Sapiens” would have become irreversible.

The Members of the seventh Parliament of Ghana’s Fourth Republic owe it as a duty to themselves, and humanity at large, to approve the current bill, “Promotion of Proper Human Sexual Right and Ghanaian Family Bill, 2021”: and put paid to the spread of the LGBTQI+ movement in Ghana.

Additionally, as the subsequent, or the ultimate course of action of the LGBTQI’s++ cannot be predicted, the Bill should contain every necessary sanctions and restraint which will empower our courts and our internal security agents to deal ruthlessly with any future outward actions and behaviours, consisted under the Bill. Indeed the expansion of the LGBTQI+ creed is not only an affront to SDG goals 3 & 5; All the 17 goals are under attack, to frustrate the Global to sustainably improve our livelihoods.

Ultimately, all that the LGBTQI+s seek for themselves before their eventual demise from this world is to shirk their responsibility related to child bearing, and the nurturing of one’s offspring.

Therefore, just like the disgruntled Epicurean Philosophies of old, all that the LGBTQI+ creed care about in life being “the runts” among humanity is aptly summed-up as follows; “Let us Eat, Drink and Be Merry, Tommorrow We Die!! As for the foreigners who have travelled to Ghana lately to surreptitiously, go from house-to-house, or from one office to another soliciting support for the LGBTQI’s++ whether they themselves are of the same creed, even if they eat one barrel full of Tuo Zaafi, or Fufuo today, and another one barrel of Jollof Rice tomorrow, the Bill will successfully go through our Parliament. Then they, and all their Ghanaian collaborators, can “Go-to-Court”, or “Go-to-Hell!!

Finally, I wish the Proposers of the Bill, and all our Parliamentarians a successful deliberation. Long live Mankind! Long Live Ghana!

SENDER

- Mr. F [REDACTED] C [REDACTED]
- [REDACTED]
- A Thinker
- A Cocoa Farmer
- Email: [REDACTED]